

Development of the Stratosphere Navigator: A Versatile Spherical Robot for Diverse Applications

Adarsh S

Dinesh S

Dharanish K

Asif Ahamed B

Abstract— In the field of robotics, spherical robots have emerged as a forefront of innovation, revealing the future of automation. This project examines the progression of spherical robots, from the Sphero toy to the Ballbot and Dyret robots, emphasizing their versatility and applicability in a variety of real-world applications. Traditional robots struggle in severe conditions, limiting extraterrestrial exploratory missions. This project seeks to create a polar robot capable of navigating diverse terrains with grace and precision while overcoming barriers with ease. The goal is to create a robotic platform that can adapt to various environments and tasks by leveraging the latest innovations, such as control system and MEMS sensor. The objective of the project is to identify the positive and negative elements of established robotics paradigms through research and analysis.

This project attempts to harness the unique capabilities of spherical robots by developing a polar robot with dynamic and precise movement abilities. By leveraging advanced microcontrollers, sensors, and innovative design concepts, the aim is to overcome existing limitations in robotic platforms. Through continuous experimentation and analysis, this work seeks to unlock new possibilities in exploration, logistics, and beyond, bridging the gap between theory and practical application. Ultimately, this endeavor aims to redefine the boundaries of traditional robotics and pave the way for transformative advancements in various domains.

Keywords—Ball Bot, Dyret robots, Polar Robots, Spherical Robots, Extraterrestrial exploratory missions, Sensors

I. INTRODUCTION

Spherical robots. They're like the Swiss Army knives of the robotic world—versatile, capable, and just plain cool. Who wouldn't want a rolling ball of technology zipping around, tackling tasks with the agility of a cat on a hot tin roof? From the playful Sphero toy, which first sparked our imaginations, to the futuristic Ballbot or the very recent Samsung's Ballie and the adaptive Dyret robots, spherical robots have come a long way. Their unique design and omnidirectional movement offer significant advantages for a wide range of applications. Traditional robotic platforms confront numerous obstacles while navigating harsh terrains and extreme environments, limiting their effectiveness in exploratory missions. In response to these restrictions, the goal of this project is to create a polar robot that can navigate varied terrains with precision and agility. The goal is to construct a robotic platform that can adapt to different settings and tasks by utilizing advanced microcontrollers, sensors, and unique design principles.

The goal is to close the gap between theoretical robotics paradigms and practical implementations through thorough

study and analysis. This project aims to overcome existing restrictions and open up new opportunities in exploration, logistics, and other fields by leveraging the capabilities of spherical robots.

Fig. 1. 2D concept

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Existing robotic platforms include an extensive variety of designs and functionalities, each tailored to a specific job and environment. Spherical robots stand out among them due to their unusual shape and omnidirectional movement capabilities, which offer promising answers to a wide range of robotics research and application difficulties. Ian Bernstein and Adam Wilson created the Sphero, a well-known spherical robot. Originally designed as a toy, the Sphero became popular due to its user-friendly control interface and sturdy build, leading to its use in educational settings and as a platform for research and development.

[1] Prof. Ralph Hollis of Carnegie Mellon University's Robotics Institute in Pittsburgh, USA, created Ballbot. The Ballbot uses a single spherical wheel to balance and move, allowing it to navigate tight places and interact with humans in a natural and intuitive way. [2] The DyRET robot, built by researchers at the University of Southern Denmark, takes a revolutionary approach to spherical locomotion. Inspired by animal shape, the DyRET has a spherical body with internal propulsion and control capabilities, allowing it to move fluidly in a variety of situations without the use of external sensors or actuators. [3] The MorpHex robot, developed by Kåre Halvorsen (aka zenta), showcases spherical locomotion and transformation. With its modular construction and flexibility to change shape and configuration, the MorpHex is a versatile platform for investigating novel locomotion tactics and adaptive behaviors in robotics. [4] The Bulebule robot, designed by engineers at the Institute of Robotics and Mechatronics at the German Aerospace Center, features a spherical body for omnidirectional movement. Utilizing an

internal pendulum mechanism for propulsion, Bulebule can navigate complex indoor environments with agility and stability. Its compact design and advanced control algorithms enable it to perform tasks such as inspection and data collection in confined spaces.

SphereX, designed for Mars exploration, has a hermetic spherical shell, rotating external parts, a LiDAR system for mapping and navigation, and an extended arm for navigating obstacles, improving its agility in difficult terrains. MIT's research focuses on spherical robots for planetary exploration, with an emphasis on characteristics like jumping and rolling to aid with data collecting and communication from deep caverns.

Spherical robots have also been used in initiatives by the European Space Agency and organizations such as Rotundus (Rotundus robot is a rather unusual spherical bot that moves using an internal pendulum) The robot was originally designed for planetary exploration at the Ångström Space Technology Center, part of Uppsala University, Sweden. Now, the designer is repurposing it for security duty here on Earth for a variety of purposes, including surveillance, security, and reconnaissance.

These activities highlight the need of creating strong propulsion mechanisms and precise control systems to enable optimal performance across a variety of terrains and operational conditions.

III. DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

A. Conceptual Design and 3D Modeling

1) 2D Concept Design

The initial phase of conceiving a 2D design involves ideation and sketching to translate conceptual ideas into tangible visual representations. Engineers and designers collaborate to brainstorm and outline the fundamental features and functionalities of the robot's components and subsystems. Through rough sketches and schematic diagrams, key design considerations such as spatial arrangement, component interconnections, and ergonomic factors are explored and refined.

During this iterative process, multiple design concepts are proposed and evaluated based on criteria such as feasibility, performance, and manufacturability. Feedback from stakeholders and interdisciplinary team members is integrated to iteratively improve the design concepts, ensuring alignment with project objectives and technical requirements.

Ultimately, conceiving a 2D design serves as a crucial preliminary step in the design iteration cycle, laying the groundwork for subsequent stages of development. By fostering creativity and collaboration, this phase facilitates the exploration of innovative design solutions and sets the stage for the transition to more detailed 3D modeling and prototyping activities.

2) 3D Design Development

In this development phase, the focus shifts towards the development of a comprehensive 3D design using Fusion 360, a flexible CAD/CAM software. Leveraging the capabilities of Fusion 360 to create a detailed digital representation of the polar robot, encompassing all essential components and structural elements. The design process involves meticulous attention to detail, ensuring that each aspect of the robot's architecture is accurately captured.

Fig. 2. Design process

Through these simulations, potential design flaws and weaknesses are identified and addressed, ensuring that the final robot design meets the desired performance criteria. By integrating 3D design development with advanced analysis techniques, this phase of the project lays the foundation for the fabrication and assembly of a robust and optimized polar robot.

Fig. 3. 3D Model View

As shown in fig.3, the 3D design isometric view provides a comprehensive visualization of the polar robot's architecture, showcasing its intricate components and structural layout in a three-dimensional space. This detailed representation offers insights into the spatial arrangement of key elements such as the ESP32 microcontroller, DC motor, L298N motor driver, and MPU6050 sensor module. With its immersive perspective, the isometric view serves as a valuable reference for assessing the overall design aesthetics and spatial relationships between different components.

B. Analysis

Performing analysis on the spherical body of the robot involves a comprehensive evaluation of its structural integrity and performance characteristics. Through finite element analysis (FEA) techniques, various aspects such as stress distribution, deformation, and thermal behavior are scrutinized to ensure optimal functionality under diverse operating conditions. By subjecting the spherical body to simulated loads and environmental factors, engineers can identify potential weak points and areas for improvement, facilitating iterative design refinement.

Dynamic simulations are conducted to assess the robot's behavior during movement and navigation. These simulations provide valuable insights into factors such as stability, balance, and maneuverability, allowing engineers to fine-tune the design parameters for optimal performance. By iteratively analyzing and optimizing the spherical body design, the project team aims to develop a robust and reliable robotic platform capable of tackling real-world challenges with precision and efficiency.

Fig. 4. Von Mises stress analysis

Von Mises stress analysis is an extensive assessment of the stress distribution throughout the structure to evaluate its mechanical robustness and potential failure locations. By simulating different loading scenarios and environmental circumstances, engineers can quantify the Von Mises stress—a measure of the material's yielding behavior. Critical areas experiencing high-stress concentrations are identified, guiding design modifications to enhance structural robustness and longevity..

C. Fabrication

Fabricating the body with Paper Mache, wood putty with PLA dust composite, and a gym ball as a Mold involves a multi-step process to create a lightweight and durable spherical structure for the robot. Initially, a 51 cm gym ball serves as a Mold to provide the desired spherical shape. Layers of Paper Mache are meticulously applied to the surface of the gym ball, gradually building up the structure and ensuring uniform coverage. Once the Paper Mache layer has dried, a mixture of wood putty and PLA dust composite is prepared and applied to the surface. This composite material offers enhanced strength and durability while maintaining a lightweight profile, making it ideal for robotic applications.

Careful attention was paid to smoothing and shaping the composite layer to achieve the desired surface finish and structural integrity. After the composite layer has cured, the gym ball mold is carefully removed, leaving behind a hollow spherical shell. Final touches such as sanding, and sealing may be applied to enhance the aesthetic appeal and protect the fabricated body from environmental factors. By Using a combination of traditional crafting techniques and innovative materials, the fabrication process results in a robust and functional body for the spherical robot.

Fabricating the body in three distinct layers improves structural integrity and longevity while delivering a smooth surface finish. The first layer, made of paper mache, is precisely applied to the gym ball mold to form the initial shape and structure of the spherical body. Following that, a layer of

canvas cloth is carefully placed to support and stabilize the overall structure.

Fig. 5. Fabrication process

Finally, a mixture of wood putty and PLA dust composite is applied, providing superior strength and resilience, ensuring the body can withstand the rigors of robotic movement and environmental conditions.

IV. CALCULATIONS AND MOTION MODEL

The spherical droids material was selected based on the following assumptions and requirements. Diameter of the base of the robot, $d = 500 \text{ mm} = 0.5 \text{ m}$

(converted from mm to m)

Radius of the robot, $r = d/2 = 0.25 \text{ m}$

Mass of the robot, $m = 5.81 \text{ kg}$

Additional pay load, $w = 2 \text{ kg}$

$$M = m + w = 5.81 \text{ kg} + 2 \text{ kg} = 7.81 \text{ kg}$$

Volume of the Sphere

$$V = 4/3 * \pi * (0.25 \text{ m})^3 = 0.065 \text{ m}^3$$

Required density ρ of the material can be calculated using the formula

$$\rho = M/V$$

$$\rho = M/V = 7.81 \text{ kg} / 0.065 \text{ m}^3 = 120.15 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

Hence, the material composite with density more: $1.200\text{E-}06 \text{ kg/mm}^3$, is selected.

A. Elementary Kinematics

A The velocity vectors at two points A and C of the rigid body:

Fig. 6. Droid velocity vector

By using the following formulas, we can determine how the angular velocity of the robot affects the linear velocity at different points on its spherical surface, aiding in stability and

maneuverability. This formula is used to predict and control the motion of the robot accurately

$$\mathbf{v}_A = \bar{\mathbf{v}} + \boldsymbol{\omega} \times (\mathbf{x}_A - \bar{\mathbf{x}})$$

$$\mathbf{v}_B = \bar{\mathbf{v}} + \boldsymbol{\omega} \times (\mathbf{x}_C - \bar{\mathbf{x}})$$

where:

$\bar{\mathbf{v}}$ is the velocity of the body,

$\boldsymbol{\omega}$ is the angular velocity,

$\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ is center of mass,

X_A and x_B are the positions of points A and C, respectively.

$\mathbf{v}_A$ and $\mathbf{v}_C$ are the required velocity of two driving motors.

B. Center of Gravity

CG or Center of Gravity is essential for determining the exact point where the robot's total weight can be considered to act, simplifying the analysis of its static equilibrium and dynamic stability.

They are critical in mechanical design and balancing efforts, ensuring that the robot rolls smoothly and remains stable during movement.

By calculating the center of gravity coordinates, engineers can design and optimize the placement of internal components to achieve desired performance characteristics, such as enhanced maneuverability and minimal energy consumption.

From an arbitrary point, P (x,y,z) as reference:

For the x-coordinate of the CG:

$$X_{cg} = \frac{\sum X_i m_i}{\sum m_i}$$

For the y-coordinate of the CG:

$$Y_{cg} = \frac{\sum Y_i m_i}{\sum m_i}$$

For the z-coordinate of the CG:

$$Z_{cg} = \frac{\sum Z_i m_i}{\sum m_i}$$

X_{cg}, Y_{cg}, Z_{cg}: These are the coordinates of the center of gravity of the robot along the x, y, and z axes, respectively.

$\sum X_i$, $\sum Y_i$, $\sum Z_i$: These represent the sum of the products of each component's coordinate and its respective mass (m_i) across all components of the robot.

$\sum m_i$: This represents the sum of all masses (m_i) of the components of the robot.

V. SOFTWARE AND INTEGRATION

The primary communication channel between the user and the spherical robot is the software integration, which is an intricate and well-designed part of the system. The smooth operation and control of the robot are made possible by the integration of multiple essential components.

A. Web Interface and Wi-Fi Network

Using the ESP32 microcontroller, the software architecture is centered on building a strong Wi-Fi network. Users can connect their devices directly to the robot, which serves as an access point. Through this connection, one can access a specially created HTML, CSS, and JavaScript web interface. In order to provide simple interaction and real-time monitoring, the interface offers a control panel with directional buttons, a speed slider, and status indications that is both intuitive and easy to use.

B. WebSocket Communication

The software makes use of WebSocket technology to enable bidirectional real-time communication between the web interface and the robot. This guarantees that the robot receives user inputs rapidly and displays its status on the web interface in a timely manner. Precise control as well as rapid feedback are made possible by the WebSocket communication, which keeps the user's commands and the robot's actions in sync.

Fig 7. Controller

VI. CONCLUSION

The project successfully demonstrated the design, development, and implementation of a spherical robot equipped with an advanced control system and MEMS sensors for terrain navigation and stability. The robot's design, inspired by existing robotic platforms such as the Ballbot and Dyret robots, showcases the versatility and adaptability of spherical robots in navigating varied terrains. By leveraging technologies such as the ESP32 microcontroller and the MPU6050 sensor, we were able to achieve real-time feedback on tilt and orientation, allowing the robot to maintain balance and stability on uneven surfaces.

The results of the project, particularly in the robot's ability to self-correct and return to its Center of Gravity (COG), were highly encouraging. As depicted in the **Tilt Angle vs. Time** graph (Fig. 8, attached below), the robot effectively adjusted its tilt in response to dynamic surface changes, settling into a stable position after a brief period of oscillation. This demonstrates the success of the feedback loop between the sensors and the control system, which allows the robot to maintain equilibrium even on sloped or irregular surfaces.

Fig 8. Tilt angle vs Time

While the existing technology serves as a good foundation for spherical robot navigation, there are various areas for further enhancement. Enhancements to the control system may improve the robot's speed and precision in stabilizing itself on more difficult terrain. Furthermore, adding machine learning techniques may enable the robot to adapt to new settings automatically, increasing its utility in interplanetary exploration and defensive duties. Another potential advancement would be to improve the materials and construction methods utilized in the robot's body, with the goal of reducing weight while maintaining durability.

Exploring other sensor technologies, such as LiDAR for obstacle identification, may also improve the robot's operational skills in unfamiliar or harsh surroundings. Ultimately, this project sets the stage for further exploration of spherical robotics, paving the way for innovations in autonomous navigation, robotics in extreme environments, and adaptive robotic platforms. Future iterations of the project could see this robot being utilized in advanced research fields such as planetary exploration, logistics, and search-and-rescue missions.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. A. E. Andersson, et al., "CasADi: A software framework for nonlinear optimization and optimal control," *Math. Program. Comput.*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 1–36, 2019.
- [2] J. Antol, "A new vehicle for planetary surface exploration - The Mars Tumbleweed Rover," 1st Space Exploration Conference: Continuing the Voyage of Discovery, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics.
- [3] M. Bujňák, et al., "Spherical robots for special purposes: A review on current possibilities," *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 22, p. 1413.
- [4] R. Chase and A. Pandya, "A review of active mechanical driving principles of spherical robots," *Robotics*, vol. 1, pp. 3–23.
- [5] X. Hou, et al., "Hydrodynamic analysis-based modeling and experimental verification of a new water-jet thruster for an amphibious spherical robot," *Sensors*, vol. 19, p. 259, 2019.
- [6] JimmyZ, "JimmyZ's BB8 build version 1: Electronics breakdown supply list," JimmyZ's BB8 Build Version 1, <https://jimmyzsbb8.blogspot.com/2016/10/electronics-breakdown-supply-list.html>.
- [7] V. A. Joshi, et al., "Design and analysis of a spherical mobile robot," *Mech. Mach. Theory*, vol. 45, pp. 130–36.
- [8] Y. L. Karavaev and A. A. Kilin, "The dynamics and control of a spherical robot with an internal omnivheel platform," *Regul. Chaotic Dyn.*, vol. 20, pp. 134–52.
- [9] I. Mia and E. L. Secco, "Design of an interactive BB8-like robot."
- [10] "MorpHex robot transforms from ball into creepy crawler," CNET, <https://www.cnet.com/culture/morphex-robot-transforms-from-ball-into-creepy-crawler/>.
- [11] W. Ren, et al., "Spherical robot: A novel robot for exploration in harsh unknown environments," *IET Cyber-Syst. Robot.*, vol. 5, p. e12099.
- [12] C. Sánchez, "How does BB-8 work?" <http://www.howbb8works.com>, Accessed 02 Feb. 2024.
- [13] M. M. Scheunemann, et al., "Human perception of intrinsically motivated autonomy in human-robot interaction," *Adapt. Behav.*, vol. 30, pp. 451–72.
- [14] L. Shi, et al., "Design, implementation and control of an amphibious spherical robot," *J. Bionic Eng.*, vol. 19, pp. 1736–57, 2022.
- [15] F. Tomik, et al., "Design, fabrication and control of Spherobot: A spherical mobile robot," *J. Intell. Robot. Syst.*, vol. 67, pp. 117–31.
- [16] UtsourceVisit, "Running DC motor with Arduino using L298N motor driver," *Instructables*, <https://www.instructables.com/Running-DC-Motor-With-Arduino-Using-L298N-Motor-Dr/>, Accessed 01 Mar. 2024.